

Synthesis and antifungal activity of some new derivatives of 5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3*H*)-thione

Nisheeth Rastogi* and Darwin Anil Harrison

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow Christian Post-Graduate College, Lucknow-226 018, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : nisheethrastogi2003@gmail.com

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Abstract : 5-{4'-(2'',4''-Dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3*H*)-thione (2) was prepared by the reaction of 4-(2',4'-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine (1) with potassium isopropylxanthate in isopropyl alcohol. 5-{4'-(2'',4''-Dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3*H*)-thione (2) on being subjected to aminomethylation with secondary amines in the presence of formaldehyde gave 3-aminomethyl-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3*H*)-thiones (3-8). Compound 2 was treated with alkyl/aralkyl/aryl halides in dry acetone in the presence of potassium carbonate to get 3-alkyl/aralkyl/aryl-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3*H*)-thiones (9-14) while when compound 2 was treated with same halides in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide, yielded 2-alkyl/aralkyl/arylthio-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (15-20). Oxadiazole 2 on reaction with acid chlorides in aqueous sodium hydroxide resulted in 2-aryl/phenylacetylthio-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (21-24). 2-Aryl-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (25-29) were obtained by refluxing benzoyl hydrazine 1 with aromatic acids in phosphorus oxychloride. The structures of the compounds were established by elemental analysis and spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR and Mass). The compounds were screened for their antifungal potential against human pathogenic fungi.

Keywords : 1,3,4-Oxadiazole-2(3*H*)-thione, aminomethylation, antifungal activity.

Introduction

In the series of five membered nitrogen, sulfur and oxygen containing heterocyclic compounds, oxadiazole nucleus has attained a unique position in the field of medicinal chemistry. Among the four isomeric forms 1,2,3; 1,2,4; 1,3,4 and 1,2,5 of oxadiazoles, 1,3,4-oxadiazole has proved its potential as the most biologically active one with wide range of biological activities viz. anticancer¹, anticonvulsant², antiinflammatory³, herbicidal⁴, antimicrobial⁵, anti-HIV⁶, antitubercular⁷, virucidal⁸, antimalarial⁹, muscle relaxant¹⁰, anthelmintic¹¹, hypnotic¹², antiproliferative¹³ and lipid peroxidation inhibitor¹⁴. Recently three review¹⁵ articles have been published on the synthesis and biological potential of substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles. Influenced by the biological activity profile of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles and in continuation¹⁶ of our work on biologically active heterocyclic compounds, here we are reporting synthesis of some new derivatives

of 5-(4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3*H*)-thione as antifungal agents.

Methyl paraben was treated with 2,4-dichlorobenzyl chloride to get methyl 4-(2',4'-dichlorobenzoyloxy)benzoate which on hydrazinolysis gave 4-(2',4'-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine (1)¹⁷. Benzoyl hydrazine (1) on treatment with potassium isopropylxanthate in isopropyl alcohol resulted in to 5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3*H*)-thione (2) which exists in two tautomeric forms thione and thiol. Compound 2 on being subjected to aminomethylation¹⁸ with secondary amines in the presence of formaldehyde gave 3-aminomethyl-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3*H*)-thiones (3-8). Compound 2 was treated with alkyl/aralkyl/aryl halides in dry acetone in the presence of potassium carbonate to give 3-alkyl/aralkyl/aryl-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3*H*)-thiones (9-14) while when compound 2 was treated with

*Address for correspondence : 231/103 Ka, Bagh Macca, Khinni Tare, Raja Bazar, Lucknow-226 003, Uttar Pradesh, India.

same halides in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide, yielded 2-alkyl/aralkyl/arylthio-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**15-20**). On reaction with acid chlorides in the presence of aqueous sodium hydroxide solution, compound **2** gave 2-aryl/phenylacetylthio-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**21-24**). 2-Aryl-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**25-29**) were obtained by refluxing benzoyl hydrazine (**1**) with aromatic acids in phosphorus oxychloride.

Antifungal activity :

Compounds **2-29** were screened for their *in vitro* antifungal potential against human pathogenic yeasts viz. *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Sporothrix schenckii* and mycelial fungi viz. *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*. The compounds were tested at 100 µg/mL concentration in DMSO by Tube Dilution Technique¹⁹. The spore suspension of 10⁵ spores/mL was used for this purpose. The drug dilutions were made serially. The test was performed at 29°C and Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) in µg/mL was recorded by visual observation after 24–72 h incubation. Suitable controls : broth control (without infection), growth control (with infection), solvent DMSO, drug controls (all test compounds) and fluconazole (as standard drug) were set under identical conditions. The last tube with no apparent growth of organism represented the MIC of compounds. The details of *in vitro* antifungal activity profile of the compounds are summarized in Table 2.

Experimental

The melting points were obtained in open capillary tubes in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (ν_{\max} in cm⁻¹) and ¹H NMR spectra on Bruker DRX-300 instrument using CDCl₃/DMSO as solvent and TMS as internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm. Mass spectra were recorded on Jeol D-300 spectrometer. Elemental analysis data were obtained on Carlo Erba 1108 analyzer. Homogeneity of the compounds was checked by TLC silica gel G plates and spots were visualized by exposure to iodine vapors. Physical data of the compounds synthesized are presented in Table 1.

5-{4'-(2'',4''-Dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione (**2**) :

A mixture of 4-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine (**1**) (0.01 mol) and potassium isopropylxanthate (0.06 mol) in isopropyl alcohol (20 mL) was refluxed for 8 h. Excess of solvent was distilled off and the residue was treated with 25 mL of ice-cold water. The clear solution so obtained was acidified with acetic acid. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and recrystallised from aq. DMF. IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 3460 (NH), 1252 (-CH₂O-), 1170 (C-O-C), 1035 (C=S), 742 (C-Cl); MS *m/z* : 353 (M⁺), 355 (M+2), 357 (M+4).

3-Aminomethyl-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thiones (**3-8**) :

5-(4'-(2'',4''-Dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione (**2**) (0.005 mol) was dissolved in minimum quantity of DMF. To this formaldehyde (0.5 mL, 37%) and secondary amines (0.005 mol) were added with vigorous stirring. The reaction mixture was warmed on a water bath for 2 min and then left overnight at room temperature. Solid compound thus obtained was filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform : petroleum ether 60–80 °C (1 : 1). **3** : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 3.11 (6H, s, Me), 4.55 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.19 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.89–7.61 (m, aromatic protons); MS *m/z* : 410 (M⁺), 412 (M+2), 414 (M+4). **5** : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 1.58–1.60 (4H, m, -CH₂CH₂-), 2.84–2.88 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.54 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.19 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.87–7.51 (m, aromatic protons); MS *m/z* : 436 (M⁺), 438 (M+2), 440 (M+4). **6** : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 1.04–1.09 (3H, t, Me), 2.17–2.24 (2H, t, -CH₂-), 2.38–2.56 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 2.60–2.78 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.54 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.19 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.87–7.88 (m, aromatic protons). **7** : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 2.38–2.56 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 2.60–2.78 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 4.44 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.19 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 6.87–8.08 (m, aromatic protons). **8** : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 2.34–2.42 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 2.50–2.68 (4H, t, -CH₂-N-CH₂-), 3.49 (2H, s, -CH₂Ph), 4.44 (2H, s, >N-CH₂-N<), 5.19 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.00–7.89 (m, aromatic protons).

Table 1. Characterization data of the compounds prepared

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Ar	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :			Molecular formula
							Found (Calcd.)			
							C	H	N	
2	-	-	-	-	220	65	50.75 (50.99)	2.75 (2.83)	7.80 (7.93)	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S
3	Dimethylamino	-	-	-	142	65	52.44 (52.68)	4.04 (4.14)	10.13 (10.24)	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S
4	Diethylamino	-	-	-	124	65	54.57 (54.79)	4.60 (4.79)	9.45 (9.58)	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S
5	Pyrrolidino	-	-	-	168	68	54.89 (55.04)	4.19 (4.35)	9.50 (9.63)	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S
6	N-Ethylpiperazino	-	-	-	162	55	55.00 (55.11)	4.90 (5.01)	11.56 (11.69)	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
7	N-Phenylpiperazino	-	-	-	144	60	59.11 (59.20)	4.47 (4.55)	10.55 (10.62)	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
8	N-Benzylpiperazino	-	-	-	100	60	59.69 (59.88)	4.76 (4.80)	10.27 (10.35)	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
9	-	Methyl	-	-	166	60	52.24 (52.31)	3.19 (3.26)	7.56 (7.62)	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
10	-	Ethyl	-	-	120	55	53.44 (53.54)	3.56 (3.67)	7.25 (7.34)	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
11	-	Benzyl	-	-	138	66	55.18 (55.28)	3.56 (3.61)	6.32 (6.23)	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
12	-	4-Chlorobenzyl	-	-	118	66	55.18 (55.28)	3.10 (3.14)	5.74 (5.86)	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ Cl ₃ N ₂ O ₂ S
13	-	2,4-Dichlorobenzyl	-	-	130	56	51.50 (51.56)	2.67 (2.73)	5.40 (5.46)	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₂ S
14	-	2,4-Dinitrophenyl	-	-	196	70	48.49 (48.55)	2.27 (2.31)	10.70 (10.78)	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₆ S
15	-	Methyl	-	-	180	66	52.26 (52.31)	3.21 (3.26)	7.56 (7.62)	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
16	-	Ethyl	-	-	143	70	53.47 (53.54)	3.60 (3.67)	7.30 (7.34)	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
17	-	Benzyl	-	-	172	63	59.50 (59.59)	3.56 (3.61)	6.27 (6.32)	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S

Table-1 (contd.)

18	-	4-Chlorobenzyl	-	124	66	55.19 (55.28)	3.10 (3.14)	5.76 (5.86)	$C_{22}H_{15}Cl_3N_2O_2S$
19	-	2,4-Dichlorobenzyl	-	142	60	51.50 (51.56)	2.79 (2.73)	5.40 (5.46)	$C_{22}H_{14}Cl_4N_2O_2S$
20	-	2,4-Dinitrophenyl	-	154	60	48.50 (48.55)	2.25 (2.31)	10.71 (10.78)	$C_{21}H_{12}Cl_2N_4O_6S$
21	-	-	Phenyl	204	60	51.59 (51.66)	2.67 (2.73)	5.38 (5.46)	$C_{22}H_{14}Cl_2N_2O_2S$
22	-	-	4-Tolyl	186	66	58.55 (58.59)	3.32 (3.39)	5.90 (5.94)	$C_{22}H_{16}Cl_2N_2O_2S$
23	-	-	4-Anisyl	166	66	56.59 (56.67)	3.24 (3.28)	5.68 (5.74)	$C_{23}H_{16}Cl_2N_2O_4S$
24	-	-	Benzyl	182	78	58.48 (58.59)	3.34 (3.39)	5.89 (5.94)	$C_{23}H_{16}Cl_2N_2O_3S$
25	-	-	-	128	55	61.78 (61.82)	3.71 (3.74)	6.52 (6.55)	$C_{22}H_{16}Cl_2N_2O_3$
26	-	-	4-Chlorophenyl	150	63	58.34 (58.40)	2.89 (3.01)	6.42 (6.48)	$C_{21}H_{13}Cl_3N_2O_2$
27	-	-	4-Nitrophenyl	152	58	57.08 (57.01)	2.89 (2.94)	9.48 (9.50)	$C_{21}H_{13}Cl_2N_3O_4$
28	-	-	Styryl	138	70	65.19 (65.24)	3.74 (3.78)	6.57 (6.61)	$C_{23}H_{16}Cl_2N_2O_2$
29	-	-	2-Hydroxyphenyl	168	70	60.89 (61.01)	3.30 (3.38)	6.74 (6.77)	$C_{21}H_{14}Cl_2N_2O_3$

Table 2. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of compounds against pathogenic fungi by tube dilution technique

Compd.	<i>Candida albicans</i>	<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	<i>Sporothrix schenckii</i>	<i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i>	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>
2	50	50	50	12.5	12.5
3	25	50	50	12.5	12.5
4	25	50	50	12.5	12.5
5	12.5	50	50	6.25	6.25
6	12.5	50	50	6.25	6.25
7	25	50	50	12.5	25
8	25	50	50	25	25
9	50	50	50	25	25
10	50	50	50	25	25
11	50	50	50	25	25
12	12.5	3.12	6.25	3.12	3.12
13	12.5	6.25	6.25	6.25	6.25
14	12.5	12.5	25	6.25	6.25
15	50	25	25	25	25
16	50	25	25	50	25
17	25	25	25	12.5	12.5
18	6.25	12.5	12.5	6.25	12.5
19	6.25	12.5	12.5	3.12	3.12
20	12.5	12.5	12.5	3.12	3.12
21	50	12.5	12.5	25	25
22	25	12.5	12.5	25	25
23	6.25	25	25	3.12	3.12
24	25	25	50	25	25
25	6.25	6.25	12.5	3.12	3.12
26	12.5	12.5	12.5	6.25	12.5
27	6.25	12.5	12.5	3.12	3.12
28	50	25	25	25	25
29	12.5	25	25	3.12	6.25
Fluconazole (Standard drug)	0.05	1.0	2.0	1.0	2.0

3-Alkyl/aralkyl/aryl-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thiones (**9-14**) :

A mixture of 5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione (**2**) (0.05 mol), anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.5 g) and alkyl/aralkyl/aryl halides (0.05 mol) in dry acetone (20 mL) was refluxed for 4-6 h on a water bath. After completion of the reaction, excess of acetone was distilled off and the residual mass was poured in ice-cold water. The separated solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether 60-80 °C (1 : 1). **9** : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3083 (Me), 1256 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 1177 (C-O-C), 1057 (C=S), 734

(C-Cl). **10** : $^1\text{H NMR}$ ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ (ppm) : 1.10-1.20 (3H, t, Me), 3.26-3.33 (2H, q, CH_2), 5.20 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 7.08-7.94 (m, aromatic protons). **11** : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 2791 ($-\text{CH}_2-$), 1251 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 1174 (C-O-C), 1041 (C=S), 733 (C-Cl); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 5.03 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 5.16 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 7.03-7.94 (m, aromatic protons); MS m/z : 443 (M^+), 445 ($\text{M}+2$), 447 ($\text{M}+4$). **13** : $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ (ppm) : 4.99 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$), 5.19 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 7.03-7.94 (m, aromatic protons). **15** : IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 1351 (NO_2), 1259 ($-\text{CH}_2\text{O}-$), 1173 (C-O-C), 1028 (C=S), 740 (C-Cl).

(a) Potassium isopropylxanthate, i-PrOH
 (b) Amines, CH₂O, DMF
 (c) Alkyl/aralkyl/aryl halides, K₂CO₃, Me₂CO
 (d) Alkyl/aralkyl/aryl halides, KOH, EtOH
 (e) Aryl/phenylacetylchlorides, NaOH
 (f) Aromatic acids, POCl₃
 Ar = 4-Anisyl, 4-chlorophenyl, 4-nitrophenyl, styryl, 2-hydroxyphenyl

R₁ = Dimethylamino, diethylamino, pyrrolidino,
N-ethylpiperazino, *N*-phenylpiperazino,
N-benzylpiperazino
 R₂ = Me, Et, benzyl, 4-chlorobenzyl,
 2,4-dichlorobenzyl, 2,4-dinitrophenyl
 R₃ = Phenyl, 4-tolyl, 4-anisyl, benzyl

Scheme 1

2-Alkyl/aralkyl/arylthio-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (15-20) :

A mixture of 5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3*H*)-thione (**2**) (0.05 mol) and alkyl/aralkyl/aryl halides (0.05 mol) in alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (25 mL, 5%) was refluxed for 5–6 h. Cooled and triturated with ice cold water. The solid mass thus obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from isopropyl alcohol. **16** : ¹H NMR

(DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 1.30–1.41 (3H, t, Me), 2.99–3.12 (2H, q, -CH₂-), 5.19 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.08–7.94 (m, aromatic protons). **17** : IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 2754 (-SCH₂-), 1257 (-CH₂O-), 1173 (C-O-C), 749 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (DMF-*d*₇) δ (ppm) : 5.16 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 4.50 (2H, s, -SCH₂-), 7.03–7.94 (m, aromatic protons); MS *m/z* : 443 (M⁺), 445 (M+2), 447 (M+4). **19** : IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 2825 (-SCH₂-), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 1172 (C-O-C), 748 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 4.42 (2H, s, -SCH₂-),

5.19 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.03–8.10 (m, aromatic protons). **20** : IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1391 (NO₂), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 1173 (C–O–C), 749 (C–Cl).

2-Aroyl/phenylacetylthio-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (21-24) :

Compound **2** (0.005 mol) was dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 30 mL) and substituted acid chlorides (0.005 mol) were added to it, dropwise, and whole contents were stirred for 1 h. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from CHCl₃ : MeOH (5 : 1). **21** : IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1680 (thioester), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 1172 (C–O–C), 748 (C–Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 5.19 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.48–8.18 (m, aromatic protons); MS *m/z* : 457 (M⁺), 459 (M+2), 461 (M+4). **23** : IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1674 (thioester), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 1172 (C–O–C), 748 (C–Cl); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 3.90 (3H, s, OMe), 5.19 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.42–8.19 (m, aromatic protons). **24** : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 3.32 (2H, s, -COCH₂-), 5.24 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.13–7.86 (m, aromatic protons).

2-Aryl-5-{4'-(2'',4''-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-phenyl}-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (25-29) :

A mixture of 4-(2',4'-dichlorobenzoyloxy)-benzoylhydrazine (**1**) (0.05 mol) and aromatic acids (0.05 mol) in phosphorus oxychloride (10 mL) was refluxed for 8–10 h. The excess of phosphorus oxychloride was distilled off *in vacuo*. The reaction mixture was poured in water and pH was adjusted to 7 by adding liq. ammonia. The precipitate so obtained was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether 60–80 °C (1 : 1). **25** : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 3.50 (3H, s, OMe), 5.19 (2H, s, -CH₂O-), 7.03–7.94 (m, aromatic protons); MS *m/z* : 427 (M⁺), 429 (M+2), 431 (M+4). **27** : IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1382 (NO₂), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 1168 (C–O–C), 740 (C–Cl). **28** : IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 3062 (-CH=CH-), 1255 (-CH₂O-), 1173 (C–O–C), 750 (C–Cl).

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